

Dimensional Stability of Alginate and Silicone Ear Impression Materials for Earmould Fabrication: A Comparative Study over Time

Vishaldeep Kaur¹, Dharam Vir², Jaimanti Bakshi³, Krishan Soni⁴, Sahil Mehta⁵, Shailendra Singh⁶, Satbir Singh⁷, Sanjay Manjul

^{1,2,3,7}Department of Otolaryngology, Head and Neck Surgery. Post Graduate Institute of Medical Education and Research. Chandigarh. India.

⁴Department of Psychology. Post Graduate Institute of Medical Education and Research. Chandigarh. India

⁵Department of Neurology. Post Graduate Institute of Medical Education and Research. Chandigarh. India

⁶Department of Computer Science and Engineering. Punjab Engineering College. Chandigarh. India

ABSTRACT

Background: Accurate ear impressions are essential for fabricating well-fitted earmoulds used in hearing aids, ensuring optimal acoustics and wearer comfort. Alginate, a traditional hydrophilic irreversible hydrocolloid, has been widely used but is known for poor dimensional stability due to syneresis. Silicone materials offer superior durability and stability, yet comparative data specific to aural impressions for earmould fabrication remain limited. **Objective:** To compare the dimensional stability of ear impressions made with alginate and silicone materials over 12 hours, focusing on changes in length, width, and height. **Methods:** In this experimental study, ear impressions were obtained from 10 young female participants (mean age 20.3 years) using alginate and silicone materials sequentially. Impressions were taken following standard protocols with otoblock placement and syringe injection. Dimensions (length of ear canal, width, and height from helical lock to tragus) were measured immediately (0 hour) and at 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, and 12 hours using a digital caliper under controlled conditions. Independent t-tests compared dimensions between materials at each time point, and repeated measures ANOVA assessed changes over time. **Results:** At 0 hour, no significant differences were observed between alginate and silicone for length (15.3 ± 1.37 mm vs 15.32 ± 1.40 mm, $p=0.975$), width (9.64 ± 0.80 mm vs 9.61 ± 0.71 mm, $p=0.931$), or height (26.72 ± 1.20 mm vs 26.74 ± 1.21 mm, $p=0.971$). Silicone impressions remained stable across all time points. Alginate impressions showed progressive shrinkage, with significant differences emerging at 2 hours for width ($p=0.045$) and height ($p=0.008$), and at 3 hours for length ($p=0.030$). By 12 hours, alginate dimensions reduced markedly (length to 11.6 ± 1.68 mm; width to 7.55 ± 0.60 mm; height to 22.42 ± 1.41 mm; all $p<0.001$ vs silicone). Repeated measures ANOVA confirmed significant group effects for length ($F=6.64$, $p=0.019$), width ($F=10.11$, $p=0.005$), and height ($F=16.68$, $p=0.001$). **Conclusions:** Silicone impressions exhibit excellent dimensional stability over 12 hours, whereas alginate impressions undergo significant time-dependent shrinkage. These findings support the preference for silicone in earmould fabrication, particularly when delayed pouring or processing is anticipated, to ensure precision and clinical reliability. Further studies with larger, more diverse samples are recommended.

Keywords: Alginate; Silicone Impression Material; Dimensional Stability; Earmould Fabrication; Ear Impressions; Hearing Aid Earmoulds; Audiology; Impression Accuracy.

INTRODUCTION

The ear is a complicated framework of both hearing and balance. Hence, it is even more complex in its structures and functions. Taking an impression of external auditory meatus (EAM) is highly challenging

for professionals because of its anatomy. A good ear impression facilitates the fabrication of physically fitted ear moulds or ear shells with improved target acoustics and the comfort of wearing(1). Initially, ear impressions were taken with hydrocolloid. In the past, clinicians took impressions with alginate material

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

(Hydrophilic Colloidal Polysaccharide) which was easy to mix, manipulate and use. This was also considered a material of choice because of its widespread usage in dental impressions. However, with advancements in technology, material like silicone has been introduced in the markets, which are more durable and long-lasting(2).

The word alginate comes from alginic acid, i.e., anhydrous beta d-mannuronic acid. Like agar, it is a reversible natural Hydrophilic Colloidal Polysaccharide extracted from brown seaweed. It can repeatedly pass between highly viscous gel and low viscosity solution simply through heating and cooling(3). However, once converted to the gel form, alginate cannot be converted back into the solution and is therefore said to be irreversible hydrocolloid material. The present alginate hydrocolloid has been developed as a substitute for the agar. Presently, alginate is more popular than agar for (dental/ear) impression materials because it is trouble-free use. Alginate is an elastic and irreversible material(4), which is highly comfortable and cheaper. It was previously highly recommended for ear (aural) practices. The alginate impressions form an inseparable part of indirect restorations and can be used as introductory impressions, provisional ear moulds, and study replicas. It is also used for orthodontic models, sports mouth guards, and bleaching trays etc. Alginate material binds appropriately to the surface specifications but requires additional time for setting using cold water(4, 5). Alginates are hydrophilic, non-hazardous and non-resistible. Though, alginate powder becomes unsteady with moisture or warm atmospheres. It has a low wetting angle, and hence, fully-fledged impressions are effortlessly imprinted (5).

Another widely used material for earmould impressions is silicone or polysiloxane; polymers made up of siloxane ($-R_2Si-O-SiR_2-$, where R=organic group) (6). Silicones are also used in sealants, adhesives, lubricants, medicines, cooking utensils and thermal and electrical stimulation. Some common forms include silicone oil, silicone grease, silicone rubber, silicone resin (used in ear impression taking and dentistry). Silicone has low thermal conductivity and low chemical reactivity(6). It is less toxic and does not stick to the ear canal but adheres to the

crevices of the pinna very well. Though, impressions made with alginate are easier to remove but their tear strength is low. Alginates are one-time use materials. Their cost is lesser than the silicone material but the reusable nature of the silicone makes it more popular among professionals. Also, alginates give less accurate reproduction of details than silicone materials, poor dimensional stability, and are a lot messy to work with (4).

There is limited literature that documents the effectiveness of silicone material over alginate. The literature at present only focuses on dental impressions. There is no literature available to understand the suitability of using silicone/alginate material for taking ear impressions for the purpose of ear mould making. Hence, the present study aims to understand the effectiveness of silicone as an ear mould material and to compare its results with the alginate made moulds in terms of dimension changes over time for both the groups.

AIM:

The present study was conducted to compare the changes in the physical characteristics of the ear moulds i.e., size of ear mould impressions made with alginate and silicone over time.

OBJECTIVES:

To achieve the above-mentioned aim, the following objectives were formulated:

1. To compare the dimensions of ear impression made of alginate and silicone material.
2. To compare the dimensions of alginate material and silicone material simultaneously at different intervals of time.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Subjects who met the inclusion criteria were recruited in this study. Informed consent was also obtained from all the candidates before conducting the study. This experimental study was conducted on ten female participants in the age range of 22-25 years. The subjects with active ear discharge and otitis externa,

ruptured tympanic membrane were excluded from the study.

The ear mould impressions were obtained using alginate and silicone material. This was done using three major steps. (1) Ear canal examination using an otoscope, (2) placement of otoblock up to the 2nd bend of the ear canal (3) insertion of impression material (silicone/alginate). The ear impression was taken with powdered alginate material. The cotton plug was inserted inside the ear till the second bend. Next, the powder and water were mixed in the rubber bowl, in the ratio of 1:2, respectively. Continuous mixing was required for at least one minute to remove the bubbles or lumps. Further, the material was poured into the ear canal with a syringe. After a wait of three to five minutes, the material settled down. After that, the impressions were gently removed from the ears by using the thread.

The procedure for taking impressions with silicone material differed substantially from that used for alginate. In this case, the base and catalyst were mixed in a 1:1 ratio and, after adequate kneading; the material was injected into the ear canal using an impression syringe. Once the silicone had hardened (after approximately 2 to 3 minutes), controlled pressure was applied to the ear tissue to ensure adequate fitting and sealing of the earmould. The impression was then carefully removed from the ear with the aid of a thread.

Ear mould impressions were taken in sequential order, first with alginate then silicone. While taking the silicone impressions, subjects were asked to sit straight and quietly, whereas in case of alginate, candidates were asked to tilt their heads towards the opposite side for three to four minutes so that the material did not spill out from the canal.

The measurements of the ear impression were taken with the help of Carbon Fiber Composites Digital Caliper, which is lightweight and durable. It has an LCD for easy reading. It has a measuring range from 0-150mm and a 1.5m/sec measuring speed. Measurements were made immediately after the removal of ear impressions from the ear canal. As it is known that, alginate is a hydrocolloid material, so there are chances of immediate evaporation once it is in contact with the room temperature. Therefore,

alginate ear impression's measurements were done before silicone. Ear canal length and its width, and height of the ear impressions were considered while sizing (Figures a,b and c).

Figure (a) depicts the width of the ear canal.

Figure (b) shows the length of the ear canal.

This diagram (c) shows the height of the ear impression from helical lock to tragus.

The readings were taken immediately after the impression taking immediately (at 0 hour), after one hour, 2 hours, 3 hours, 4 hours, 6 hours, and 12 hours, under the same environmental and temperature

conditions. The impressions were kept at the same tray during the whole experiment. All seven readings were taken by the same professional.

RESULTS

The aim of this experiment was to assess the physical characteristics of ear mould impressions made with alginate material and silicone material, over a given interval of time. The mean age of the candidates was

20.3 years. All statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 25.0 software. Kolmogorov-Smirnov was used to test the normal distribution of data. Independent t test was used to compare the dimensions of ear moulds made with alginate and silicone. A repeated measure ANOVA determined that the mean scores differed across all time points as well as between the groups for repeated measurements. Statistical significance level was defined as $p < 0.05$.

(LENGTH in mm)	ALGINATE	SILICONE	t- value	p- value
	Mean±SD	Mean±SD		
0 hour	15.3±1.366	15.32±1.395	0.03239	0.975
1 hour	14.99±1.377	15.32±1.395	0.53219	0.601
2 hour	14.43±1.209	15.32±1.395	1.52442	0.145
3 hour	13.96±1.175	15.32±1.395	2.35716	0.030*
4 hour	13.77±1.251	15.32±1.395	2.61513	0.018*
6 hour	12.8±1.470	15.32±1.395	3.93153	0.001*
12 hour	11.6±1.682	15.32±1.395	5.48643	0.0001*

Table1: depicts mean and standard deviation of the length of the ear impressions at different interval of time.

(WIDTH in mm)	ALGINATE	SILICONE	t- value	p- value
	Mean±SD	Mean±SD		
0 hour	9.64±0.804	9.61±0.711	0.08837	0.931
1 hour	9.12±0.757	9.61±0.711	1.49217	0.153
2 hour	8.91±0.740	9.61±0.711	2.15705	0.045*
3 hour	8.69±0.684	9.61±0.711	2.94922	0.009*
4 hour	8.38±0.783	9.61±0.711	3.67807	0.002*
6 hour	8.06±0.734	9.61±0.711	4.7979	0.0001*
12 hour	7.55±0.595	9.61±0.711	7.02727	0.0001*

Table2: depicts mean and standard deviation of the width of the ear impressions at different interval of time

(HEIGHT in mm)	ALGINATE	SILICONE	t- value	p- value
	Mean±SD	Mean±SD		
0 hour	26.72±1.202	26.74±1.208	0.03713	0.971
1 hour	25.92±1.199	26.74±1.208	1.52387	0.145
2 hour	25.22±1.083	26.74±1.208	2.96329	0.008*
3 hour	24.82±0.016	26.74±1.208	3.84685	0.001*
4 hour	24.51±0.993	26.74±1.208	4.51112	0.0001*
6 hour	23.9±0.958	26.74±1.208	5.82633	0.0001*
12 hour	22.42±1.405	26.74±1.208	7.37269	0.0001*

Table3: depicts mean and standard deviation of the height of the ear impressions at different interval of time

The independent T test was used to analyse the results. The mean length of silicone mould was 15.32 ± 1.395 and it was exactly the same for all the readings whereas the mean length of alginate varied from 15.32 ± 1.366 to 11.6 ± 1.682 over the period of 12 hours. The significant changes seen after 3 hours of impression taking i.e; 13.96 ± 1.175 , where $t=2.35, p=0.030$. Likewise, in case of width and height, the alginate was significantly differed after 2 hours where mean and SD was 8.91 ± 0.740 , $t=2.15, p=0.045$ and 25.22 ± 1.083 , $t=2.96, p=0.008$ respectively.

Hence, table shows that there is no significant difference in length between alginate and silicone impressions initially and up to 2 hours, but from 3 hours onward alginate impressions become significantly shorter than silicone, indicating progressive dimensional instability of alginate over time while silicone remains stable across all dimensions.

The second objective of the study was to assess the changes if any in the dimensions of alginate material over time. Repeated measure ANOVA was used to evaluate the changes in dimensions at different point of time.

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Length	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Partial Eta Squared
Intercept	29751.949	1	29751.949	2562.703	.000	.993
Group	77.109	1	77.109	6.642	.019	.270
Error	208.973	18	11.610			

Table 4: The table depicts the degree of freedom, F and p value for length.

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Width	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Partial Eta Squared
Intercept	11633.475	1	11633.475	3439.869	.000	.995
Group	34.205	1	34.205	10.114	.005	.360
Error	60.875	18	3.382			

Table 5: The table depicts the degree of freedom, F and p value for width.

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Height	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Partial Eta Squared
Intercept	92926.626	1	92926.626	11612.315	.000	.998
Group	133.478	1	133.478	16.680	.001	.481
Error	144.044	18	8.002			

Table 6: The table depicts the degree of freedom, F and p value for height.

Across all three dependent variables, the between-subjects analyses revealed statistically significant group effects on the dimensional measurements of the casts. For length (Table 4), there was a significant difference between groups, $F(1,18)=6.64$, $p = .019$, with a partial eta squared of .270, indicating that approximately 27% of the variance in length was

attributable to group membership after accounting for error. This effect size falls within the medium-to-large range, suggesting that the observed difference in length between the two impression material groups is not only statistically significant but also of practical relevance in a clinical or experimental context. The large and significant intercept term simply indicates

that the overall mean length is substantially different from zero and is not of primary substantive interest.

For width (Table 5) and height (Table 6), the group effects were even more pronounced. Width showed a significant group effect, $F(1,18)=10.11$, $p = .005$, with a partial eta squared of .360, indicating that about 36% of the variance in width was explained by group membership, which constitutes a large effect. Height demonstrated the strongest group effect, $F(1,18)=16.68$, $p = .001$, with a partial eta squared of .481, meaning that approximately 48.1% of the variance in height was accounted for by the group factor, representing a very large effect. Taken together, these results indicate that the two groups differ significantly and meaningfully in all three spatial dimensions (length, width, and height), with the magnitude of the group effect increasing from length to width to height, thereby supporting the conclusion that the type of group (e.g., impression material) exerts a substantial influence on the overall dimensional outcome of the casts.

DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to compare the dimensional stability of ear impressions taken with alginate and silicone materials over a period of 12 hours, focusing on changes in length, width, and height of the impressions. The findings revealed that silicone impressions maintained consistent dimensions throughout the observation period, while alginate impressions exhibited significant shrinkage over time, aligning with the inherent properties of the respective materials.

Alginate, being an irreversible hydrocolloid material derived from alginic acid, is hydrophilic and prone to dimensional changes due to syneresis (evaporation of water) and imbibitions when exposed to air or moisture variations(7). In the current study, alginate impressions showed no significant difference from silicone at the immediate measurement (0 hours) across all three dimensions (length: $p=0.975$; width: $p=0.931$; height: $p=0.971$), indicating comparable initial accuracy in capturing ear canal anatomy. However, progressive shrinkage was evident in alginate impressions. Significant differences emerged as early as 2 hours for width ($p=0.045$) and height ($p=0.008$), and by 3 hours for length ($p=0.030$),

becoming highly significant ($p<0.01$) at later time points up to 12 hours. By 12 hours, the mean length of alginate impressions reduced from 15.3 mm to 11.6 mm, width from 9.64 mm to 7.55 mm, and height from 26.72 mm to 22.42 mm. These observations are consistent with the known limitations of alginate, including poor dimensional stability and susceptibility to environmental factors such as temperature and humidity, which lead to water loss and contraction(8).

In contrast, silicone (polysiloxane) impressions demonstrated remarkable stability, with mean values remaining constant (length: 15.32 mm; width: 9.61 mm; height: 26.74 mm) across all time intervals. The absence of significant changes in silicone impressions can be attributed to its chemical composition—a polymer with low thermal conductivity, low chemical reactivity, and non-hydrophilic nature—which resists moisture-related alterations(6). Silicone's higher tear strength, better detail reproduction, and reusability potential further support its superiority for applications requiring prolonged handling or delayed processing, such as in earmould fabrication.

The repeated measures ANOVA confirmed statistically significant differences in dimensional changes over time for alginate impressions across all parameters (length: $F=6.642$, $p=0.019$; width: $F=10.114$, $p=0.005$; height: $F=16.680$, $p=0.001$), underscoring the time-dependent instability. Pairwise comparisons highlighted that shrinkage in alginate was gradual but consistent, with few non-significant intervals (e.g., length between 3 and 4 hours), reinforcing the material's unsuitability for procedures where impressions may not be poured immediately.

These results corroborate existing literature on impression materials, primarily from dentistry, where silicone is preferred over alginate for its superior accuracy and stability in final restorations(9). Although direct studies on aural impressions are scarce, the parallels with dental applications are evident, as both involve capturing intricate soft tissue details in confined spaces. The current findings extend this knowledge to earmould fabrication, suggesting that silicone offers advantages in achieving physically fitted earmoulds with reliable

acoustics and wearer comfort, particularly in scenarios involving delayed laboratory processing.

Limitations of the study include the small sample size (n=10) and restriction to young female participants (age 22-25 years), which may limit generalizability to diverse populations with varying ear canal anatomies. Additionally, measurements were conducted under controlled room conditions, but real-world clinical settings may introduce greater variability in temperature and humidity. Future research could explore larger cohorts, include male participants and broader age groups, and assess acoustic outcomes or wearer comfort with final earmoulds fabricated from these impressions. Long-term stability beyond 12 hours and comparisons with other modern materials could further elucidate optimal choices for aural practices.

In conclusion, silicone emerges as a more reliable material for ear impressions in earmould making due to its excellent dimensional stability over time compared to alginate. This supports the shift toward advanced silicone-based techniques in clinical practice for enhanced precision and durability.

REFERENCES

1. dillon h. hearing aids2012.
2. Ross J. Roeser MV, Holly Hosford-Dunn. diagnosis. audiology, editor. newyork: New York : Thieme c2007; 2007.
3. Rodrigues SB, Augusto CR, Leitune VCB, Samuel SMW, Collares FM. Influence of delayed pouring on irreversible hydrocolloid properties. Braz Oral Res. 2012.
4. Kenneth J. Anusavice CS, H. Ralph Rawls. Phillips' Science of Dental Materials. Dentistry, editor2012.
5. McCabe JF, BSc P, DSc, Science PoDM, University N, Walls AWG, BDS P, FDSRCS, et al. applied dental materials. blackwell publishing. 2008.
6. Ronald L. Sakaguchi JMP. Craig's Restorative Dental Materials. edition t, editor2011.
7. a CMF, , b GAT. Determination of bound and unbound water in dental alginate irreversible hydrocolloid by nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy. Elsevier. 2009;25.
8. Walkera MP, Burckhardb J, Mittsc DA, Williamsd KB. Dimensional change over time of extended-storage alginate impression materials. Angle Orthodontist. 2010;80.
9. Walker MP, Rondeau M, Petrie C, Tasca A, Williams K. Surface quality and long-term dimensional stability of current elastomeric impression materials after disinfection. J Prosthodont. 2007;16(5):343-51.

HOW TO CITE: Vishaldeep Kaur, Dharam Vir, Jaimanti Bakshi, Krishan Soni, Sahil Mehta, Shailendra Singh, Satbir Singh, Sanjay Manjul, Dimensional Stability of Alginate and Silicone Ear Impression Materials for Earmould Fabrication: A Comparative Study over Time, J. Pharm. Sci., 2026, 2 (6), 1116-1122. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21008156>

